

SHAPING THE THINKING OF YOUTHS BY PROMOTING THE IDEA OF NATIONAL RECOVERY - NATIONAL UPGRADE

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Abstract: It will be possible to ensure the independence of the nation, its uniqueness only as a result of national ideas, their transformation into material power. The national idea begins to form in the process of self-realization of young people. National development has an evolutionary character, it is a continuous process of the formation, improvement and rise of the nation. National revitalization is a process related to the reorientation of the lost potential due to certain reasons at a certain stage of the history of the nation's development to the development of the nation.

Keywords: national development model, people, nation, socio-political, economic and spiritual development, state management methods, regional and global integration strategy, development and renewal

After gaining independence, Uzbekistan chose a unique and appropriate way of development and renewal in the economic, social, political, ideological and spiritual spheres. The experience of our republic's transition to a market economy, the "unique and suitable" path of development, the new theory of statehood based on our national traditions from the first days of independence, the idea of national revival, strategic issues planned in the future, regional and international politics, the place and position of Uzbekistan in the world community, etc. issues have been developed.

Also, the characteristics of the legal democratic state being built in Uzbekistan, democracy and the spirit of the people, the development of democratic principles, the synthesis of cultures and civilizations, the ways of forming a civil society system, the need for a national ideology and its foundations, the restoration of national values, and the conceptual ideas of studying our history of thousands of years were explained.

It is known that the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, said: "Let us have a free and prosperous Motherland!" who put forward the noble idea, and this motto took a deep place in the hearts of all of us, the whole nation, and fulfilled this great task with honor at all times, in any situation, and

in this way, he did not spare his incomparable energy and intelligence, even his precious life when necessary. . It is Islam Karimov, who has seen a lot, that our country gained independence in a very difficult historical period, achieved great achievements in restoring our national statehood and taking a worthy place in the world community, developing and implementing the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, reforming all spheres and branches of life, all of this free and will never forget that it is a solid foundation for our prosperous life. Of course, at certain stages of the development of society, the attitude to social events is manifested in different ways. Today, such a path has become the most acceptable goal for many countries that have their own sovereignty. Jonahon A new era has begun in the many thousand-year history of our country - the era of freedom and liberation, national revival and development. Of course, it is natural for all of us, the whole nation, to repeatedly remember today that the historical services of the First President Islam Karimov were incomparable in achieving these achievements.¹

It is known that Islam Karimov started working as the head of our republic² at the time (June 23, 1989) in our country for many years Communist ideology and one-sided economic policies based only on the supply of raw materials had begun to show their destructive negative effects on a large scale in every sector. If we pay attention to the reality in the sources, it shows the following situation in the difficult and sad socio-political landscape of that time.

In particular, the republic was in one of the last places in the country, far behind the average level in the Union in terms of all main economic and social indicators. Uzbekistan ranked 12th in the country in terms of gross social product production per capita, and the indicator of national income production per capita was two times lower than the average level in the Union. In terms of labor productivity in industry, the republic lags behind the country by 40%, and in terms of labor productivity in agriculture, it lags twice.

he production of consumer goods per capita in the republic was only 40% of the Union average, and it was one of the last among the Union republics in terms of income level and consumption of basic products. On average, the population of Uzbekistan consumes twice as much meat products, milk and dairy products, and eggs as compared to the population of the country as a whole. The share of

¹ Mirziyoev Sh.M. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The speech of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the twenty-sixth anniversary of the Independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan. <https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/981>

² Karimov I.A. Uzbekistan is on the threshold of independence.-T.: Uzbekistan, 2011. 327 p.

the population with an average gross income of less than 5 soums per month was slightly more than 12 percent in the country, but it reached 45 percent in our republic.

Social infrastructure networks: health care, public education, preschool institutions were in a very bad condition, 60% of schools and hospitals were located in unusable buildings, and there were very acute economic and social problems in a situation of crisis. Considering that our republic is mainly a base of raw materials, a source of raw materials for industrial ministries and agencies, the local, socio-economic features of the country are sometimes not sufficiently evaluated, sometimes completely, and sometimes these features are not even appreciated.

Time and life itself Islam Karimov is a mature politician of our time, a famous leader who can see the essence of the extremely complex events happening in the world and in different regions from the point of view of statesmanship, who deeply feels a great sense of responsibility for his country and people, for the fate of each of our compatriots. confirmed.

In the most tense and dangerous period of our national history, when various conflicts have flared up, there is a risk of war between nations and citizens in our country, the economy is in a difficult situation, in short, the administration and state policy carried out at a time when the life of the old regime is ending and a new era is beginning, The historical reforms in the meaning have undoubtedly been of decisive importance in the further destiny and development of Uzbekistan and the Uzbek people.

As Sh.M. Mirziyoev noted, the founder of the independent state of Uzbekistan, a great state and political figure, a great and honorable son of the Uzbek people, the First President of our country, Islam Karimov, freed our country from the dependence of the authoritarian system and restored our country, which was on the verge of destruction. Our Great Leader turned Uzbekistan into a modern democratic state developing rapidly and steadily in a historically short period of time despite severe difficulties and trials in an extremely volatile and dangerous situation³.

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³Mirziyoev Sh.M. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. On perpetuating the memory of Islam Abdugʻanievich Karimov, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent, January 27, 2017

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The word Harakat in the strategy of actions is from the Arabic word for agitation

was taken and used in the sense of inciting and awakening all layers of the population to enlightenment, initiative, creative progress in the field of national development of Uzbekistan. Such a stirring movement will lead the country to the development of national upliftment.

Development is a type of changes and actions that take place in nature and society in the transition from one quality to another or from one state to another. The process of development begins with social change. Changes are made through social, economic, spiritual, cultural and political spheres. That is, as a result of the exchange of the quantitative, meaningful, structural state of each field, quality indicators are created. However, any changes do not ensure development. Changes lead to development with holistic programs.

Development is manifested in the process of complexification and improvement of the social system, its effective adaptability to external conditions, the expansion of the scope of reality, the growth of quantity and quality in any field, and the creation of structural arrangements for its practical support.⁵

Today, ideas such as the formation of a free and prosperous, humane and just state and a strong civil society are supported by all layers of our society. Fulfillment of large-scale tasks related to the implementation of the idea of

⁴ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017. —In 2017-2021

About the strategy of action on the five priority areas of development on the Republic of Uzbekistan Website National database of legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan – www.lex.uz

⁵ Alimardonov T. Action strategy - Uzbekistan's national development is at a new stage. People's word. 29.01.2019

"Rising" is an important condition for the stable development of our country. People of different nationalities and peoples, religions and denominations, state and public organizations, living under the same sky and working towards a common goal in our country, act in the same political arena. serves to further strengthen mutual respect and solidarity between the representatives of the participating parties.

References:

1. Mirziyoev Sh.M. The founder of the independent state of Uzbekistan. // Islam Karimov.-T.: Republican Charitable Public Fund named after Islam Karimov 2018. -10 p.
 2. President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev's speech at the ceremony dedicated to the twenty-sixth anniversary of the Independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan. <https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/981>
 3. Karimov I.A. Uzbekistan is on the threshold of independence.-T.: Uzbekistan, 2011. 327 p.
- Mirziyoev Sh.M. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. On perpetuating the memory of Islam Abdug'anievich Karimov, the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent, January 25, 2017
5. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017. –In 2017-2021
 6. On the strategy of action on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan||// Website National database of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan – www.lex.u
 7. Alimardonov T. Action strategy - Uzbekistan's national development is at a new stage. People's word. 29.01 2019

